

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DELINQUENT BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENTS

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The changes occurring in our society have brought forward a number of problems, one of which is the problem of delinquent behavior in adolescence. Everyday we can observe antisocial behavior of people. The tense social situation causes the growth of various deviations in personal development and behavior of people; to a greater extent, this affects adolescents whose value structure has not yet been formed, and the immaturity of personality manifests itself. In Russian psychology, the study of delinquent behavior was carried out by E.V. Zmanovskaya, V.I. Dobrenkov, A.E. Lichko, and others. In foreign psychology, this issue is actively studied in the research of the American Psychological Association, R. Baron, E. Diener, and others.

Adolescence is a time of character formation. The environment and the immediate surroundings exert a huge influence. An adolescent's behavior is an external manifestation of the complex process of their character formation. Often, serious behavioral disorders are associated with deviations in this process. Adolescents strive for independence and autonomy, and overestimate their capabilities. Moral concepts, principles, and values are formed, and they do not always correspond to legal norms, as a result of which criminal actions are committed.

The problem of delinquent (unlawful, antisocial) behavior is central to the research of most social sciences, since public order plays an important role in the development of both the state as a whole and each citizen individually. Based on the

analysis of scientific literature, it can be concluded that delinquent behavior is mostly understood as the actions of a specific individual or a social group that deviate from the laws or rules established in a given society.

Delinquent behavior is understood as the actions of a specific individual that deviate from the laws established in a given society and at a given time, threatening the well-being of other people or the social order, and are criminally punishable in their extreme manifestations. Consideration of the social factors of such behavior will help identify the characteristics of this phenomenon, as well as create relevant programs for the prevention of delinquent behavior.

As a consequence, the analysis of literature showed that in domestic science, delinquency is used in two different meanings. For example, A.E. Lichko and other researchers argue that delinquency consists of repeated antisocial offenses that build up into a certain stable stereotype of actions that violate legal norms, but do not entail criminal liability due to their limited public danger or because the individual has not reached the age from which criminal liability begins [1]. In his time, this point of view was contested by V.V. Kovalev and his followers, who viewed delinquency as criminality. In particular, E.V. Zmanovskaya, adhering to the position of V.V. Kovalev, notes that delinquent behavior represents "the actions of a specific individual that deviate from the laws established in a given society and at a given time, threatening the well-being of other people or the social order, and are criminally punishable in their extreme manifestations. An individual exhibiting illegal behavior is qualified as a delinquent, and the actions themselves as delicts" [2]. At the same time, as already emphasized, the term "delinquency" is still not a priority in Russian science. In modern psychology, a fairly wide range of words corresponding to foreign concepts of delinquency (unlawful, criminogenic, criminal behavior, etc.) is used.

T.V. Shipunova emphasizes that "delinquency" in the narrow sense denotes such behavior of children, adolescents, and youth that could be called criminal if it were demonstrated by adults. U.S. Pozdnyakova understands the delinquent behavior of adolescents as a variation of their deviant behavior with such a degree of severity of social consequences under which a minor violates the legal norms prevailing in a given society, and which is expressed, as a rule, in the commission of offenses or crimes representing an increased public danger, as well as in the persistent opposition of the minor to the surrounding reality [3].

In accordance with the problem under study, attention is drawn to the research of S.V. Marishin, dedicated to the analysis of psychological barriers in the communication of juvenile convicts. He distinguishes the following types: adaptive, motivational-semantic, emotional, and communicative barriers. From the author's point of view, the specific features of the manifestation of psychological barriers of delinquents in situations of deprivation of liberty consist in the intensity of internal conflict between a positive and an immoral attitude toward a number of behavioral norms of a member of society. The internal conflict of the convict's personality is resolved in specific life situations in favor of immoral aspirations. S.V. Marishin associates the psychological barriers of delinquents with problems in the emotional sphere (aggressiveness, depression, irritability, emotional lability, subjective feeling of loneliness, anxiety, frustration, rigidity). At the same time, adolescents highly value such moral qualities as love for parents, kindness, openness, mercy, and hospitality [4].

In the view of I.S. Kon, "there is practically no single social or psychological aspect of the behavior of adolescents or youths that does not depend on their family conditions in the present or the past" [5]. Thus, a significant role in the origin of delinquent behavior, besides personality traits, is undoubtedly played by the micro-social situation, the core of which is composed of intra-family dysfunction and

traumatic events experienced by the adolescent, which are environmental factors in the formation of delinquent behavior in adolescents.

Delinquent behavior can develop according to the principle of a vicious circle. After an initial, possibly accidental crime, a person undergoes punishment, subsequently difficulties of adaptation arise, due to the label of a "criminal" an accumulation of difficulties occurs, and the person commits a repeated crime [6]. Another cause of delinquency can be an unfair assessment of punishment for offenses. The micro-social situation has a significant impact on the formation of delinquent behavior. Factors causing delinquency include: – Frustration of the child's need for care and attention from parents. The child experiences pain and, in the absence of understanding, turns to disappointment and anger. Aggression attracts the parents, and the child begins to achieve their goals in this way. Gradually, this becomes systematic and the consolidation of delinquent behavior occurs. – Violence, the use of punishment, physical and psychological cruelty exert the strongest influence on the child. – Conflicts between parents observed by the child. – Undesirable personality traits of parents (a combination of an undemanding father and an indulgent mother) [7].

Thus, delinquent behavior in adolescents is more likely to form in families where the primary style of upbringing by the mother is hyperprotection, indulgence, and severity of punishment in the absence of clear requirements against the background of emotional rejection. The reasons for unharmonious upbringing by mothers of adolescents vary. Sometimes these are certain circumstances in family life that prevent the establishment of adequate communication with children. Frequently, the main role in the violation of the educational process is played by the personality traits of the parents themselves. In such families, adolescents experience crisis situations much more frequently, accompanied by neuropsychic tension, pronounced anxiety, and instability of self-esteem. The study revealed that

delinquent adolescents spend little time with their parents, rarely ask them for help, do not make efforts to earn their praise, and prefer not to depend on their advice and guidance. At the same time, minors sincerely believe that they are not loved or recognized in the family, and are denied support. Adolescents feel that they are not accepted as individuals, are little trusted, are subjected to criticism and authoritarian influence, and they are not left by a sense of loneliness in their family [8].

Delinquent behavior is formed in an adolescent mainly under the influence of environmental factors, the most important of which can be considered the violation of relationships in the family system, in particular, in the style of mothers' upbringing, since it is the mother who plays the most significant role in the formation of the child's personality. At the same time, delinquent behavior is more frequently formed in adolescents who have experience of traumatic events of a high degree of intensity, such as the death of loved ones, divorce of parents, or the entry of parents into a new marriage. This is due to the fact that in adolescence, during the period of intensive formation of the Self-concept, accompanied by contradictory experiences, polar evaluations, and sometimes an acute feeling of inferiority, the loss of one of the parents for a child can be a loss of the basic sense of security.

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